

GOALS AND DUTIES OF THE ORGANIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM OF THE YANGI MUSEUM IN UZBEKISTAN

Yulduz Pirnazarovna Urunbaeva

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, PhD, docent

Abstract: the purpose and tasks of organizing and developing new museum tourism in the national tourism of Uzbekistan are presented in the article. Also, proposals for the development of museum tourism are recommended.

Keywords: museum, muse, mythology, herbarium, collection, civilization, antiquities, exhibit, integration, concept, tragedy, comedy, poetry.

Introduction. To further improve the system of museums formed in the territory of Uzbekistan, to increase their role in the spiritual and moral maturity of the people, to carefully preserve, study, enrich, take out and promote the rich history of our nation and the steps of our independence preserved in the museum funds, In the minds of our people, important issues such as national pride and pride, independence and loyalty to the Motherland, and providing museums with highly qualified specialists are emerging.

The fact that the issues of tourism development are included in the decisions of our government requires the creation of new directions and new types of tourism in national tourism. That is, museology faced the social, economic and political problems of modernity. The authors of the new museum concept are introducing new methods of communication with the community in the museum. In modern life, museums should deviate from their traditional tasks and functions and implement wider programs that help them actively participate in the life of society[5]. One of such broad programs is the creation of a new tour in the national tourism of our country - "Museum tourism".

Analysis of literature on the topic. You can get acquainted with many studies about the emergence and formation of museums. Alexander the Great sent 30,000 talents to his teacher Aristotle from the wealth stolen as a result of his victories in Asia. With these funds, Aristotle established a museum of natural history. Aristotle asked his royal student to always send a sample of unknown plants from new lands (herbarium-plant museum), some new animal carcasses (dried form) (animal museum). This was the beginning of the first museums and museology [7].

"Museum" is a Greek term derived from the word "muse". In ancient Greek mythology, the deities of art and science were referred to as "muses" . It is believed that muses, that is, deities or gods, inspire poets and artists. That is why the Muse was often addressed at the beginning of the works of ancient poetry. There were many books on art, literature, and history. Among the ancient poets, Hesiod (7th century BC) lists 10 deities [6]:

1. Clio-history; 2. Euterpa - poetry and music; 3. Talia-comedy; 4. Melpomena-tragedy; 5. Terpsichora-game; 6. Erato-love lyrics;
7. Polygylenia-hymns; 8. Urania - astronomy; 9. Calliope - epic; 10. Apollo is considered the god of the Muse [7] (Figure 1).

1-Fig. Muses are gods

The image of the muse found its expression in European art. Deities - statues of various shapes are kept in sacred buildings with special respect. People visit the deities and pray for their wishes to come true. As a result, the dargah, where the muses are located, became a place of pilgrimage for people. The most original items, rare, valuable items and beautiful works of art are stored in this Dargah. Along with decorating the courtyard of this building, they also left a special impression on the hearts of pilgrims. "Museum" means a place where beautiful things are kept and where inspirations gather.

Museum tourism is also studied by Russian scientists [2, 3, 4, 8]. In these studies, the goals and objectives of the development of museum tourism in Russia are recommended. From these conclusions, we should understand the role and importance of the development of national museum tourism in Uzbekistan. Articles or any information about museum tourism in Uzbekistan have not been published until now.

Research methodology. Analytical and statistical analyses, results of the scientific expedition were used in the research.

Analysis and results. The spirituality of any nation or nation cannot be imagined without its history and national values. Therefore, the cultural and historical monuments of our old land, unique artifacts, thousands of years old finds and objects, rare manuscripts, which have made an incomparable contribution to the world civilization, are rare examples of the heritage of not only our people, but the world. Museums play a special role in preserving such priceless wealth, deeply studying our national history and traditions, analyzing and promoting them on a scientific basis, honoring the memory of our ancestors, especially the spiritual upliftment of the young generation. Museums

provide a great service to increase the aesthetic taste of a person and ensure his spiritual maturity. These settlements, which store historical and cultural objects, go back to the distant past. Museums connect society with history.

The use of museums in our country is of great importance in the development of tourism in our republic. In particular, in the social and educational life of our people, in the cultural maturity of the young generation, in shaping the expansion of human knowledge, increasing the use of our museums in tourism remains one of the most important problems.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On measures for the innovative development of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan"[1] (Tashkent city, August 26, 2018) the following is established:

- creation of an infrastructure for the population, primarily the young generation, allowing viewing of museum exhibits through the wide introduction of innovative information technologies in the activities of museums and the creation of digital forms of museum exhibits using the Internet;

- ensuring the full integration of museums into the social space in order to popularize and promote the cultural and historical heritage of our country;

- extensive use of inclusive methods of providing services and providing convenience to persons with limited opportunities, elderly visitors, children of preschool age and accompanying persons in museums.

This Decision starts the development of museums in our country. The national tourism of our country should also contribute its effective scientific and practical researches and efforts to this development. That is why it is necessary to start organizing and developing museum tourism in the national tourism of Uzbekistan. Secondly, in recent years in our country, the interest and visits of our people, especially the young generations, to museums, and the initiative to organize these visits, as well as the interest of the peoples of the world, international tourists, and heads of state who have visited our homeland, are increasing year by year. Because Uzbekistan has internationally known and famous museums. Therefore, specialists in tourism education should master the mechanisms of organizing and developing the use of museums in tourism in the form of "Museum tourism".

Object of museum tourism: museums and their activities in Uzbekistan.

The object of museum tourism is to educate people, inculcate values, understand imaginations and feelings through museum exhibits.

The purpose of museum tourism is to develop recommendations on the methodological and organizational-economic mechanisms of organization and development of museum tourism in Uzbekistan.

Tasks of museum tourism:

- to substantiate the concept, content and essence of museum tourism as a new promising tour in the national tourism of Uzbekistan, the factors that increase the socio-economic indicators of the population;

- justifying the objective necessity of developing museum tourism in educating the young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland in the conditions of globalism;

- Development of conceptual directions for the organization and development of museum tourism in Uzbekistan;

- Creation of resources, types, classification and definitions of museum tourism in Uzbekistan;

- opportunities and problems of developing museum tourism in Uzbekistan, developing recommendations on them;

- Creation of recommendations for the development of domestic and international museum tourism in Uzbekistan;

- Development of priorities for the development of museum tourism in the innovative economy of Uzbekistan.

Conclusions and suggestions. In Uzbekistan , the following researches should be carried out in order to increase socio-economic efficiency and methods of increasing socio-economic prosperity of the population through the organization and development of museum tourism:

- To determine the possibilities of assessing the impact of museum tourism on the socio-economic development of the country;

- Creation of museum tourism information-advertising centers, routes, excursions, training of museum tourism tour guides;

- Development of directions for the development of domestic and international museum tourism in Uzbekistan;

- Researching the economic effectiveness of the development of museum tourism services in providing new jobs;

- Determining the strategic directions and future of museum tourism development.

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